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IS THERE ANY POSSIBILITY OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' CONFIDENCE LEVEL IN SOLVING ECOLOGY-RELATED PROBLEMS USING SCIENCE-BASED PUZZLES AND SPACED TEACHING APPROACHES? A FIELD REPORT

¹ Samuel Terver Agamber, PhD & ² Victor Oluwatosin Ajayi, PhD

¹ Department of Biology Education, College of Education, Oju, Benue State

² Department of Science Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria

Corresponding Email: drvictorajayi@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study investigated the possibility of improving students' confidence level in solving ecology-related problems using science-based puzzles and spaced teaching approaches. A pretest, post-test, control group, quasi-experimental research design was adopted in this study. The instruments used for data collection was Ecology Confidence Scale Integrated with Test (ECSIT). ECSIT and the lesson plans were validated by three experts in Science Education/Measure and Evaluation. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula was used to test internal consistency of ECSIT which yielded a reliability value of 0.96. The population of the study was 8,571 students offering biology comprising 4,602 males and 3,969 females in 2,283 senior secondary schools in Benue State. The sample for this study was 281 SS2 Biology students from six government grant aided secondary schools in Benue State drawn using Multistage sampling technique. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using frequency count and percentage distribution scores while the null hypotheses were tested using results from Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that the observed mean difference in the confidence scores among the groups was significant [$F_{2, 274}=3346.99, P<0.05$]. It was found that there is no significant difference between the mean confidence level of male and female students taught Ecology using Science-Based Puzzles Approach (SPA) [$F_{1, 91}=1.25, P>0.05$] and Spaced Teaching Approach (STA) respectively [$F_{1, 89}=5.83, P>0.05$]. It was recommended among others that Biology teachers should be encouraged to use science-based puzzle and spaced teaching approaches in their lessons so as to improve students' confidence in solving ecology-related problems.

Keywords: Science-based Puzzles Approach (SPA), Spaced Teaching Approaches (STA), Confidence level and Ecology

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1. Introduction

Biology is a practical-based subject which equips students with concepts and skills that are useful in solving the day to-day problems of life. Ajayi (2017) observe that the importance of Biology spreads to various professions such as pharmacy, medicine, engineering, nursing, food technology, public health, veterinary medicine, biotechnology, nanotechnology and Agriculture. It is obvious that no student intending to study the aforementioned disciplines can do without Biology. Despite the strategic roles which Biology plays in boosting the scientific and technological growth as well as educational system of nations, it has been observed that the self-confidence of students that

offer the subject has been poor and which have invariably affected their academic performance (Masuzi, 2018). The Chief Examiner's Annual Reports of West African Examinations Council (WAEC, 2021) also confirmed this trend. confidence as a feeling of self-worth or self-doubt about one's ability. Confidence level is the ability of a person to believe in himself or herself and the strength to succeed Confidence level is considered one of the most influential motivators and regulators of behaviour in people's everyday lives (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Confidence is the ability to make decisions and judgments without depending on others.

National Research Council NRC (2014) asserts that in a responsive environment that rewards performance and the outcomes people expect depend heavily on their level of confidence that they can perform the skill or task. Syeda and Neeraj (2019) emphasize that students' confidence level towards science also affect courses and career choices. As such, confidence as a psychological phenomenon in the teaching and learning process cannot be overstressed. The major goal of science teaching is to help students to develop confidence towards science learning for better academic performance. Manisha (2020) observe that students' confidence level is a major barrier to their excellent performance in science. The author further emphasizes that many factors correlate with students' confidence level, among them are previous performance, interest, critical thinking abilities, gender and teaching strategies. Okoli (2020) further stresses that instructional approaches could be designed in a manner that would enable students build a certain level of confidence in their actions and decisions. Akanbi and Kolawole (2021) opine that, one of the most significant problems in implementing science curriculum and developing confidence in students has been the use of ineffective approaches to teaching.

Ajayi and Audu (2023) lamented that despite the emphasis on activity-based learning approaches for students by the National Policy on Education, it is glaring that teachers still use traditional approaches to teach science. This has not really yielded the desired results judging from the recurring poor performance of students in Secondary School Certificate Examinations. By implication, this appears to be the outcome of students' poor confidence level towards learning of the subject. Therefore, there is need to sustain students' confidence level towards learning biology by using teaching approaches that make understanding of concepts and facts easier. This implies that teachers should help students to acquire the knowledge and skills that would equip them to learn the subject, principles and knowledge for effective learning outcomes especially in difficult concepts such as Ecology. Ecology being the focus of this study is an aspect of Biology that students perceive difficult as observed by the researcher. It is one of the key topics in Biology syllabus that are taught throughout senior secondary school levels in Nigeria. Ecology is the study of the distribution and

abundance of organisms, the interaction between organisms, their environment, the structure and functions of ecosystems.

A highly motivated student is usually the one who has a high confidence level in the subject he/she is learning. Therefore, in order to improve and sustain students' confidence towards learning of Ecology, teachers must motivate students through their teaching strategies. Similarly, Ezeaku and Ezeoba (2016) observe that science teachers are familiar with the use of a number of teaching approaches but more especially the conventional approaches like discussion and demonstration approaches. The use of discussion approach which is one among the approaches that are commonly used by Biology teachers has still not produced the expected results (Nnorom, & Obikeze, 2018). Shapiro (2013) observes that any effort to tackle poor performance in Biology without considering students' confidence level will prove abortive. Based on these views by different researchers, the present study therefore investigated the possibility of improving students' confidence level in solving ecology-related problems using science-based puzzles and spaced teaching approaches.

Puzzle-based teaching refers to the use of puzzles in order to enhance higher-order thinking skills like problem solving. A science-based puzzle is an approach of teaching which involves the use of games in teaching scientific knowledge such as laws, facts, concepts and skills. These games are referred to as science puzzles. According to Slocum (2012), a science puzzle is a problem designed as a mental challenge. Solving a puzzle often provides a rewarding experience. Science puzzles do help learners to think and solve problems on their own. The author further stresses, that a puzzle can be constructed intentionally or is used to stimulate thinking for potential solutions. A puzzle is a problem or enigma that tests the ingenuity of the solver. In a puzzle, one is intended to put together pieces of information in a logical way to come up with the desired solution. Spaced teaching involves a lesson consisting of three inputs spaced by two 10 minutes break which students spend doing physical activities such as ball games, juggling and practice paper cutting into different shapes (Ajayi & Audu, 2023). The first input is a lecture in which the teacher presents the learning contents (information, materials, facts and skills). Students then go on 10 minutes break. The second input focuses on recall of the content presented earlier; the teacher represents

the content in a slightly different way, verbatim, or students may recall some practical or solve mathematical problems relating to the contents earlier presented. A second 10 minutes break is again observed. The third input focuses on understanding where students now carry out tasks by applying the knowledge or skills and confirming the facts. The breaks are 10 minutes long because this time period is enough to allow the pathway created to be "rested" before the next stimulation to strengthen the neural pathways recording the information or skills. The distracter activities (such as juggling and ball games) during the break are also different as this minimizes the danger of disrupting the pathways being formed. Hence, the study investigated the possibility of improving students' confidence level in solving Ecology-related problems using science-based puzzles and spaced teaching approaches.

1.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the proportion of students with misplaced and correct level of confidence scores that were taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach, spaced teaching approach and discussion approach?
2. What is the proportion of students by gender with misplaced and correct level of confidence taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach and spaced teaching approach?

1.2 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of students taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach, spaced teaching approach and discussion approach.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of male and female students taught ecology using science-based puzzle approach.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of male and female students taught ecology using spaced teaching approach.

2. Methods

The study employed pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design. The study area was Benue

State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 8,571 students offering biology comprising 4,602 males and 3,969 females in 2,283 senior secondary schools in Benue State. The sample for this study was 281 SS2 Biology students from six government grant aided secondary schools in Benue State drawn using Multistage sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection was Ecology Confidence Scale Integrated with Test (ECSIT). ECSIT is a researcher made instrument that contains two sections. Section A contains bio-data information of the respondents, while section B contains 30 multi-choice objective items questions with each item carried a confidence rating scale with options such as Certainly Correct (CC), Not Sure (NS) or Certainly Wrong (CW) to determine the certainty or otherwise of the correctness of the students' answers. Items for this test (integrated with confidence scale) instrument were selected from Biology past question papers of WAEC from year 2014 to 2023. These items covered areas under ecology such as nutrient cycling in nature, ecological management, pollution, conservation of natural resources, adaptation and tolerance. Forty items were set to cover the topics. Ecology Confidence Scale Integrated with Test (ECSIT) was validated by three experts of Science Education and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation all from Benue State University, Makurdi. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument before it was used. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the CAPT reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.96. The experimental groups were taught using science-based puzzles and spaced teaching approaches while the control group was taught using the conventional approach (discussion approach). The first week began with administration of ECSIT as pre-test in all the classes. The treatment began in the second week and continued to the sixth week. In the seventh and eighth weeks, there was general review of all topics taught. After the treatment, the ECSIT were administered to experimental and control groups as post-test under the same condition to ascertain the effect of the treatment. The research questions were answered using frequency count and percentage distribution scores while the null hypotheses were tested using results from Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA)

3 Results

3.1 Research Question 1

What is the proportion of students with misplaced or correct level of confidence taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach, spaced teaching approach and discussion approach? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

Table 1: *Proportion of Students with Misplaced and Correct Level of Confidence Taught Ecology using Science-Based Puzzles, Spaced Teaching and Discussion Method*

		Science-based Puzzles		Spaced Teaching Group		Discussion Group	
		Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)	Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)	Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)
Item 1	Wrong	88.9	11.1	92.2	7.8	97.9	2.1
	Correct	17.6	82.4	20.7	79.3	96.8	3.2
Item 2	Wrong	79.0	21.0	90.2	9.3	92.6	7.4
	Correct	17.4	82.6	20.6	79.4	92.0	8.0
Item 3	Wrong	91.2	8.8	89.4	10.4	91.6	8.4
	Correct	6.7	93.3	7.6	92.4	90.0	10.0
Item 4	Wrong	77.7	22.3	88.2	11.8	77.7	22.3
	Correct	21.9	78.1	11.5	88.5	8.9	91.1
Item 5	Wrong	97.9	2.1	73.9	26.1	73.9	26.1
	Correct	18.7	81.3	19.6	80.4	69.0	31.0
Item 6	Wrong	73.2	26.8	76.6	23.4	90.2	9.8
	Correct	28.3	71.7	8.9	91.1	7.2	92.8
Item 7	Wrong	69.0	31.0	48.6	51.4	85.2	14.8
	Correct	21.5	78.5	21.1	78.9	84.0	16.0
Item 8	Wrong	97.9	2.1	96.6	3.4	94.7	5.3
	Correct	11.8	88.2	22.9	77.1	92.0	8.0
Item 9	Wrong	85.7	14.3	91.8	8.2	73.9	26.1
	Correct	7.2	92.8	9.7	90.3	69.0	31.0
Item 10	Wrong	88.9	11.1	79.5	20.5	88.9	11.1
	Correct	25.4	74.6	27.2	72.8	15.4	84.6
Item 11	Wrong	80.7	19.3	73.7	26.3	95.9	4.1
	Correct	10.5	89.5	16.4	83.6	90.0	10.0
Item 12	Wrong	97.9	2.2	86.8	13.2	93.4	6.6
	Correct	18.7	81.2	12.5	87.5	72.2	27.8
Item 13	Wrong	83.9	16.1	87.5	12.5	91.2	8.8
	Correct	7.2	92.8	21.2	78.8	50.0	50.0
Item 14	Wrong	90.0	10.0	84.2	15.8	91.3	8.7
	Correct	9.0	91.0	18.8	81.2	80.0	20.0
Item 15	Wrong	72.7	27.3	94.6	5.4	95.5	4.5
	Correct	20.4	79.6	21.9	78.1	83.3	16.7
Item 16	Wrong	83.3	16.7	95.8	4.2	94.7	5.3
	Correct	10.8	89.2	20.0	80.0	93.0	7.0
Item 17	Wrong	89.8	10.2	91.4	8.6	94.7	5.3
	Correct	26.7	73.3	27.3	72.7	91.7	8.3
Item 18	Wrong	86.7	13.3	89.7	10.3	95.7	4.3
	Correct	6.3	93.7	5.3	94.7	94.1	5.9
Item 19	Wrong	25.0	75.0	83.1	16.9	93.8	6.2
	Correct	10.9	89.1	6.7	93.3	91.5	8.5
Item 20	Wrong	71.4	28.6	79.5	20.5	84.2	15.8
	Correct	13.8	86.2	27.2	72.8	84.0	16.0
Item 21	Wrong	90.5	9.5	96.0	4.0	92.1	7.9
	Correct	6.9	93.2	11.9	88.1	89.4	10.6
Item 22	Wrong	97.6	2.4	94.1	5.9	95.7	4.3
	Correct		100.0	4.0	96.0	90.1	9.9

Item 23	Wrong	89.3	10.7	94.6	5.4	95.0	5.0
	Correct	6.0	94.0		100.0	87.8	12.2
Item 24	Wrong	14.2	85.8	92.9	7.1	100.0	0.0
	Correct	8.8	91.2	12.3	87.7	89.5	10.5
Item 25	Wrong	97.8	2.2	86.7	13.3	96.2	3.8
	Correct	18.7	81.2	15.6	84.4	95.6	4.4
Item 26	Wrong	89.9	10.1	93.3	6.7	96.4	3.6
	Correct	12.5	87.5	5.2	94.8	94.7	5.3
Item 27	Wrong	93.7	6.3	95.0	5.0	96.1	3.9
	Correct	9.0	91.0	12.8	87.2	94.1	5.9
Item 28	Wrong	83.3	16.7	94.3	5.7	93.5	6.5
	Correct	14.5	85.5		100.0	90.5	9.5
Item 29	Wrong	97.9	2.1	94.6	5.4	91.3	8.7
	Correct	18.7	81.3	11.3	88.7	89.2	10.8
Item 30	Wrong	94.1	5.9	98.1	1.9	94.6	5.4
	Correct	13.0	87.0	5.4	94.6	92.3	7.7

Table 1 reveals the proportion of students with misplaced (Certainly Wrong) and correct (Certainly Correct) level of confidence taught ecology using Science-Based Puzzles, Spaced Teaching and Discussion approaches. The data in Table 1 show that for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21, 22, 24 and 27 students in Science-Based Puzzles group had higher correct level of confidence than those students in spaced teaching and discussion groups respectively. In the same vein, the table also reveals that for items 7, 12, 18, 19, 23, 25, 26, 28, 29 and 30 students in spaced teaching group had higher correct level of confidence than those students in science-based puzzles and discussion groups respectively. Similarly, the table reveals that for items 4, 6 and

10, students in discussion group had higher correct level of confidence than those students in science-based puzzles and spaced teaching groups. By implication, the students in science-based puzzles group had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 17 items, while students in spaced teaching group had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 10 items and students in discussion group had higher correct level of confidence in only 3 items. This implies that students taught ecology using science-based puzzles had higher confidence level than those taught using spaced teaching approach. Similarly, students taught Ecology using spaced teaching had higher confidence level than those taught using discussion approach

3.2 Research Question 2

What is the proportion of students by gender with misplaced and correct level of confidence taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach? The answer to research question two is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Proportion of Students by Gender with Misplaced and Correct Level of Confidence Taught Ecology using Science-Based Puzzles and Spaced Teaching Approach

		Science-based Puzzles Group				Spaced Teaching Group			
		Male		Female		Male		Female	
		Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)	Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)	Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)	Certainly Wrong (%)	Certainly Correct (%)
Item 1	Wrong	87.5	12.5	87.4	12.6	88.4	11.6	87.9	12.1
	Correct	20.6	79.4	21.7	78.3	10.9	89.1	18.6	81.4
Item 2	Wrong	82.1	17.9	83.3	16.7	87.1	12.9	86.3	13.7
	Correct	18.4	81.6	20.6	79.4	12.7	87.3	18.6	81.4
Item 3	Wrong	90.8	9.2	89.6	10.4	88.6	11.4	89.3	10.7
	Correct	10.7	89.3	9.6	90.4	13.5	86.5	11.6	88.4
Item 4	Wrong	77.7	22.3	78.1	21.9	87.1	12.9	88.1	11.9
	Correct	10.9	89.1	8.5	91.5	9.8	90.2	11.3	88.7
Item 5	Wrong	87.9	12.1	87.8	12.2	87.9	12.1	87.1	12.9
	Correct	13.7	86.3	10.6	89.4	11.1	88.9	14.6	85.4

Item 6	Wrong	78.7	21.3	80.9	19.1	86.5	13.5	85.9	14.1
	Correct	20.4	79.6	23.1	76.9	20.4	79.6	10.1	89.9
Item 7	Wrong	75.1	24.9	75.6	24.4	82.6	17.4	75.6	24.4
	Correct	21.1	78.9	15.1	84.9	19.5	80.5	15.1	84.9
Item 8	Wrong	94.1	5.9	93.9	6.1	90.3	9.7	89.9	10.1
	Correct	7.8	92.2	11.7	88.3	10.4	89.6	9.7	90.3
Item 9	Wrong	88.9	11.1	89.2	10.8	85.9	14.1	89.2	10.8
	Correct	8.8	91.2	11.3	88.7	7.4	92.6	10.3	89.7
Item 10	Wrong	80.9	15.1	80.9	19.1	87.4	12.6	87.6	12.4
	Correct	10.1	88.9	20.3	79.7	11.0	89.0	10.3	89.7
Item 11	Wrong	86.7	13.3	86.9	13.1	88.6	11.4	86.9	13.1
	Correct	7.5	92.5	5.3	94.7	9.9	90.1	12.3	87.7
Item 12	Wrong	87.9	12.1	87.3	12.7	88.9	11.1	87.8	12.2
	Correct	8.8	91.2	5.1	94.9	11.2	88.8	9.1	90.9
Item 13	Wrong	85.7	14.3	86.4	13.6	83.2	16.8	84.4	15.6
	Correct	10.3	89.7	13.2	86.8	12.3	87.7	9.2	90.8
Item 14	Wrong	87.6	12.4	87.9	12.1	90.3	9.7	89.9	10.1
	Correct	12.7	87.3	11.4	88.6	14.4	85.6	12.4	87.6
Item 15	Wrong	79.9	20.1	80.6	19.4	89.3	10.7	88.6	11.4
	Correct	10.7	89.3	12.9	87.1	7.4	92.6	9.9	90.1
Item 16	Wrong	83.3	16.7	84.7	15.3	89.3	10.7	88.7	11.3
	Correct	12.8	87.2	15.8	84.2	10.1	89.9	15.8	84.2
Item 17	Wrong	90.4	9.6	90.8	9.2	90.4	11.6	88.8	11.2
	Correct	16.1	83.9	20.3	79.7	16.1	89.9	9.3	90.7
Item 18	Wrong	87.7	12.3	87.9	12.1	88.6	11.4	89.9	10.1
	Correct	2.9	97.1	1.1	98.9	7.9	92.1	6.1	93.9
Item 19	Wrong	84.3	15.7	84.1	15.9	88.3	11.7	89.1	10.9
	Correct	7.6	92.4	8.7	91.3	7.1	92.9	8.7	91.3
Item 20	Wrong	81.7	18.3	80.5	19.5	86.5	13.5	87.5	12.5
	Correct	10.3	89.7	20.1	79.9	12.2	87.8	10.1	89.9
Item 21	Wrong	87.6	12.4	88.8	11.2	88.5	11.5	88.1	11.9
	Correct	8.7	91.3	7.9	92.1	5.2	94.8	8.0	92.0
Item 22	Wrong	87.8	12.2	88.7	11.3	88.8	11.2	88.7	11.3
	Correct	10.9	89.1	7.0	93.0	7.9	92.1	7.0	93.0
Item 23	Wrong	88.1	11.9	89.3	10.7	89.1	10.9	89.3	10.7
	Correct	10.7	89.3	7.6	92.4	20.1	79.9	21.6	78.4
Item 24	Wrong	18.2	81.8	82.9	17.1	77.2	22.8	78.9	21.1
	Correct	9.8	90.2	11.3	88.7	7.3	92.7	1.3	98.7
Item 25	Wrong	95.3	4.7	95.4	4.6	90.3	9.7	90.4	9.6
	Correct	12.2	87.8	10.6	89.4	7.7	92.3	8.6	91.4
Item 26	Wrong	86.9	13.1	87.3	12.7	87.3	12.7	88.3	11.7
	Correct	10.1	89.9	11.5	88.5	8.0	92.0	1.9	98.1
Item 27	Wrong	88.7	11.3	90.3	9.7	86.3	13.7	88.5	11.7
	Correct	5.9	94.1	6.8	93.2	4.3	95.7	6.8	93.2
Item 28	Wrong	87.1	12.9	91.1	8.9	87.9	12.1	88.3	11.9
	Correct	11.0	89.0	8.1	91.9	7.7	92.3	12.1	87.9
Item 29	Wrong	90.1	9.9	92.6	7.4	90.1	9.3	89.6	10.4
	Correct	13.9	86.1	15.1	84.9	17.1	82.9	15.1	84.9
Item 30	Wrong	90.7	9.3	93.1	6.9	85.3	14.7	85.1	14.9
	Correct	7.2	92.8	5.1	94.9	1.8	98.2	5.1	94.9

Table 2 reveals the proportion of students by gender with misplaced (Certainly Wrong) and correct (Certainly Correct) level of confidence taught ecology using Science-Based Puzzles. The data in Table 2 show that for items 1, 2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 24, 26, 27 and 29 male students had higher correct level of confidence than their female counterpart. In the same vein, the table also reveals that for items 4, 5, 7, 11, 12, 14, 18, 21, 22, 23, 25, 28 and 30 female students had higher correct level of confidence than their male counterpart. By implication, the male students in science-based puzzles group had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 17 items while their female counterpart had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 13 items. This implies that, male students taught Ecology using science-based puzzles had slightly higher confidence level than their female counterpart. Table 2 further reveals

the proportion of students by gender with misplaced (Certainly Wrong) and correct (Certainly Correct) level of confidence taught Ecology using Spaced Teaching Approach. The data in Table 9 show that for items 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 9, 11, 15, 16, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27, 28 and 30 male students had higher correct level of confidence than their female counterpart. In the same vein, the table also reveals that for items 3, 6, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26 and 29 female students had higher correct level of confidence than their male counterpart. By implication, the male students in spaced teaching group had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 16 items. On the contrary, female students had higher correct level of confidence in a total of 14 items. This implies that, male students taught Ecology using spaced teaching approach had slightly higher confidence level than their female counterparts

3.3 Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of students taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach, spaced teaching approach and discussion approach.

Table 3: Two-Way ANCOVA for Mean Confidence level Scores of Students Taught Ecology using SPA, STA and Discussion Approach.

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	191.51 ^a	6	31.92	1129.36	.00	.96
Intercept	30.58	1	30.58	1082.17	.00	.79
TprCL	.02	1	.02	.65	.42	.00
Group	189.19	2	94.59	3346.99	.00	.96
Gender	.189	1	.19	6.68	.01	.02
Group * Gender	.07	2	.04	1.26	.29	.01
Error	7.74	274	.03			
Total	1619.16	281				
Corrected Total	199.25	280				

a. R squared = .96 (Adjusted R Squared= .96)

Table 3 presents the two-way ANCOVA result for mean confidence level scores of students taught Ecology using Science-based Puzzles Approach (SPA), Spaced Teaching Approach (STA) and Discussion Approach (DA). The data in Table 3 revealed that the observed mean difference in the confidence scores among the groups was significant [$F_{2, 274}=3346.99, P<0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean confidence scores of students taught Ecology using SPA, STA and DA

was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean confidence scores among the groups. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.96 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value is considered as large effect size. This implies that 96.1% of the difference or variance in the confidence scores among the groups was explained by the treatments. Hence, the difference in the confidence scores among the groups has a large statistical effect size.

Table 4: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Confidence level Scores of Students' Taught Ecology using SPA, STA and DA.

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
SPA	DA	1.76*	.03	.00
STA	DA	1.72*	.03	.00
STA	SPA	-0.03	.03	.66

Table 4 showed Bonferroni post-hoc comparison for mean confidence level scores of students taught Ecology using Science-based Puzzles Approach (SPA), Spaced Teaching Approach (STA) and Discussion Approach (DA). The results revealed that the mean difference (I-J) between SPA and DA is 1.755* and this is significant as $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean confidence level scores between the students taught Ecology using SPA and those taught using DA in favour of students in SPA group. Likewise, the results reveal

that the mean difference (I-J) between STA and DA is 1.72* and this is significant as $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean confidence level scores between the students taught Ecology using STA and those taught using DA in favour of students in STA strategy group. However, the paired comparison of STA and SPA showed a mean difference of -0.031 and this is not significant as $p > 0.05$. This indicates no significant difference in the mean confidence scores between students taught using SPA and STA.

3.5 Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of male and female students taught ecology using science-based puzzles approach.

Table 5: ANCOVA Result for Confidence level of Male and Female Students Taught Ecology using Science-Based Puzzles

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.06 ^a	2	.03	1.19	.31	.03
Intercept	18.29	1	18.29	756.63	.00	.89
Tpr ^{CL}	.03	1	.03	1.08	.30	.01
Gender	.03	1	.03	1.25	.27	.01
Error	2.20	91	.02			
Total	765.83	94				
Corrected Total	2.26	93				

a. R squared = .03 (Adjusted R Squared= .00)

ANCOVA Test result in Table 5 revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean confidence level of male and female students taught Ecology using Science-Based Puzzles Approach (SPA) [$F_{1, 91} = 1.25, P > 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that SPA enhanced both male and female students' confidence in Ecology. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.014 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value is considered as small

effect size. This implies that only 1.4% of the difference in the confidence level scores of male and female students taught Ecology was explained by SPA. Hence, the difference in the confidence level of male and female students taught Ecology using science-based puzzles approach has very small statistical effect size. Males generally showed a higher level of confidence than females and this was consistent on the three methods.

3.6 Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference between the mean confidence level scores of male and female students taught ecology using spaced teaching approach.

Table 6: ANCOVA Result for Confidence level of Male and Female Students Taught Ecology using Spaced Teaching Approach

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.36 ^a	2	.18	5.02	.01	.10
Intersect	13.43	1	13.43	374.20	.00	.81
Tpr ^{CL}	.15	1	.14	4.14	.05	.04
Gender	.21	1	.21	5.83	.02	.06
Error	3.19	89	.04			
Total	737.49	92				
Corrected Total	3.55	91				

a. R squared = .10 (Adjusted R Squared= .08)

ANCOVA Test result in Table 6 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean confidence level of male and female students taught Ecology using Spaced Teaching Approach (STA) [$F_{1, 89} = 5.83, P > 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore retained. This means that STA enhanced both male and female students' confidence in Ecology. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.061 which is considered as small effect size. This implies that 6.1% of the difference in the confidence level scores of male and female students taught Ecology was explained by STA. Hence, the difference in the confidence level scores of male and female students taught Ecology using STA has small statistical effect size.

4. Discussion

This research was on any possibility of improving students' confidence level in solving ecology-related problems using science-based puzzles and spaced teaching approaches. The finding of this study revealed that the difference in the confidence level among students taught Ecology using Science-based Puzzles Approach (SPA), Spaced Teaching Approach (STA) and Discussion approach was statistically significant. The post-hoc comparison for the confidence level scores among the groups revealed that students taught Ecology using science-based puzzles approach had significantly higher confidence level than their counterparts taught using spaced teaching and discussion approach. Though, there was a scarcity of literature on effect of SPA on students' confidence in science subjects. This finding confirms Abidoye and Afolabi (2013) and Ajayi (2019) who found that students improved significantly in their learning outcomes

in Social Studies and Chemistry respectively using science-based puzzles approach compared to those taught using conventional teaching method. Thus, the likely explanation for this outcome may be attributed to the fact that the science-based puzzles approach enhances learners to think logically, provoke thought, and problem-solving skills thereby enhancing students' confidence about their ability to solve ecology related problems compared to discussion approach that only promotes passive learning.

The post-hoc comparison for the confidence scores among the groups also revealed that students exposed to STA had significantly higher confidence than those taught using discussion method. Though, there was a scarcity of studies on effect of STA on students' confidence in science subjects before. But this finding is in line with Adamu (2016) and Ajayi and Audu (2023) who reported that students improved significantly in their achievement and psychomotor skill in Algebra and Chemistry respectively when taught using spaced teaching approach compared to those taught using conventional teaching method. This could be because the use of STA provides a format for students to see how scientific knowledge is developed through the process of reflecting on what they know and thereby enhancing students' confidence about his/her ability to solve Ecology related problems compared to discussion method that only promotes passive learning. Therefore, if spaced teaching approach is implemented in classroom, it could enable students to understand how concepts and processes are meaningfully learned, thereby enhancing students' confidence in Ecology.

It was also found that students exposed to SPA had slightly higher confidence than their counterparts using STA but the post-hoc comparison for the confidence scores among the groups further revealed that the difference in the confidence scores between students taught Ecology using science-based puzzles approach and those taught using spaced teaching approach was not statistically significant. There was a scarcity of studies on comparison between SPA and STA on students' confidence in science subjects before. However, the likely explanation for this outcome may be attributed to the fact that both SPA and STA are used to help students develop a cognitive structure that enable students to understand the structure of knowledge and process of knowledge construction, thereby enhancing students' confidence to solve Ecology related problem.

The study revealed that male students had slightly higher confidence than their female counterparts using SPA. ANCOVA test shows that the difference was no significant. This implies that, the difference in the confidence of male and female students taught Ecology using SPA was not statistically significant. This means that SPA enhanced both male and female students' confidence in Ecology. This finding agrees with Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) who found that crossword-picture puzzle teaching strategy enhance students' achievement regardless of gender in Basic Science. However, the finding contradicts the finding of Umoru (2017) who found that female students had better attitude toward Biology than their male counterparts using puzzle-based learning strategy. The study also found that male students had slightly higher confidence than their female counterparts using STA but ANCOVA test shows that the difference was no significant. This implies that the difference in the confidence of male and female students taught Ecology using spaced teaching approach was not statistically significant. This means that STA enhanced both male and female students' confidence in Ecology. Therefore, if either SPA or STA is implemented in classroom, it will enhance students' confidence or trust about their ability to solve Ecology related problems using SPA and STA irrespective of gender. Thus, in order to encourage gender equivalence in confidence in Ecology concept, either SPA or STA should be embraced by biology teachers.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that students in the science-based puzzle group that were taught Ecology using science puzzles had higher confidence level scores than those in the spaced teaching and the discussion approach. However, the difference in the confidence level scores of students in science-based group and spaced teaching were not significant. This implies that these teaching approaches encouraged students to take control of their learning (as they are learner-centered approaches). This makes students more confidence in their thinking when compared with the discussion group. Based on this the following recommendations are made:

1. Biology teachers should be encouraged to use science-based puzzle and spaced teaching approaches in their lessons so as to improve students' confidence in solving ecology-related problems.
2. Both male and female students should be involved in SPA and STA activities to enhance their confidence level in solving ecology related problems. This is because the approaches are not gender sensitive.
3. Ministries of Education and professional bodies such as STAN should organize workshops, seminars and symposia from time to time to popularize and sensitize Biology teachers on the integration of science-based puzzle approach and spaced teaching approach in teaching ecology.

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